

Finite strain parametric HFGMC prediction of the micromechanical behavior of composite

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Research Highlights

Motivation:

Finite-strain mechanical behavior of composite materials is of great interest. For example, composite such as reinforced rubber and soft tissues can reach more than 200% of stretch, and therefore a suitable micromechanical analysis tool must be used for the prediction.

Highlights:

1. Extension of the micromechanical parametric HFGMC to incorporate the finite-strain mechanical behavior of composites
2. Establish a new incremental virtual-work-balance principle for the global finite-strain parametric HFGMC equations
3. Characterization of the constitutes mechanical behavior using energy-based functions
4. Comparison of the results with the orthogonal HFGMC as well as the FEA results

P-HFGMC Finite-Strain Methodology

Displacement $\Delta \mathbf{u}^{(\beta)} = \Delta \mathbf{u}^0 + \Delta \mathbf{w}_0^{(\beta)} + \frac{1}{2}(\Delta \mathbf{w}_2^{(\beta)} - \Delta \mathbf{w}_4^{(\beta)})r_2 + \frac{1}{2}(\Delta \mathbf{w}_3^{(\beta)} - \Delta \mathbf{w}_1^{(\beta)})r_3$
 $+ \frac{1}{4}(\Delta \mathbf{w}_2^{(\beta)} + \Delta \mathbf{w}_4^{(\beta)} - 2\Delta \mathbf{w}_0^{(\beta)})(3r_2^2 + r_2r_3 - 1)$
 $+ \frac{1}{4}(\Delta \mathbf{w}_1^{(\beta)} + \Delta \mathbf{w}_3^{(\beta)} - 2\Delta \mathbf{w}_0^{(\beta)})(3r_3^2 + r_2r_3 - 1)$

Deformation Gradient $\Delta \mathbf{F}^{(\beta)} = \Delta \mathbf{F}^0 + \mathbf{A}_w^{(\beta)} \Delta \mathbf{w}^{(\beta)}$

First Piola-Kirchhoff Stress $\Delta \mathbf{T}^{(\beta)} = \mathbf{R}^{(\beta)} \Delta \mathbf{F}^{(\beta)}$

Virtual-Work Balance $\delta \mathbf{F}^0, \mathbf{T} \mathbf{I}_{F^0}^{(\beta)} + \delta \mathbf{w}^{(\beta)}, \mathbf{T} \mathbf{I}_w^{(\beta)} = \int_{V^{(\beta)}} \delta \mathbf{F}^{(\beta)}, \mathbf{T} \mathbf{T}^{(\beta)} dV$

Global Residual

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_w^{es} \\ \mathbf{R}_{F^0}^{es} \end{Bmatrix} \equiv \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{P}_w \\ \mathbf{P}_{F^0} \end{Bmatrix} - \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_w \\ \mathbf{I}_{F^0} \end{Bmatrix} \approx \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix}$$

Incremental Solution

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \int_V \mathbf{A}_w^T \mathbf{R} \mathbf{A}_w dV & \int_V \mathbf{A}_w^T \mathbf{R} dV \\ \int_V \mathbf{R} \mathbf{A}_w dV & \int_V \mathbf{R} dV \end{Bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \Delta \mathbf{w} \\ \Delta \mathbf{F}^0 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix}$$

Results: Transverse tensile analysis

Square-array RUC with 1180 subcells and 1215 nodes of a 25% fiber-volume-fraction, and 816 subcells and 857 nodes of a 5% fiber-volume-fraction unidirectional composite

Transverse First Piola-Kirchhoff stress, $T_{22}^{(\beta)}$, distribution at $F_{22}^0 = 1.15$ for the 5% FVF composite (a), and $T_{22}^0 - F_{22}^0$ response results for 5% and 25% FVF (b).

C_{10}^m (MPa)	C_{01}^m (MPa)	κ^m
0.3	0.1	3.0
E^f (MPa)	ν^f	
22.04	0.25	

Hyperelastic compressible Mooney-Rivlin

$$W = C_{10}(\bar{I}_1 - 3) + C_{01}(\bar{I}_2 - 3) + \kappa/2 (J - 1)^2$$

Results: Equally-biaxial transverse compression

In-plane first Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor field distribution results for the case of a 25% FVF unidirectional composites undergoing equally-biaxial transverse deformation gradient at $F_{22}^0 = F_{33}^0 = 0.875, 0.8125, 0.750$ presented in the left, middle and right columns, respectively.

Conclusions

1. The Parametric HFGMC has been extended for the finite-strain micromechanical analysis of composites
2. The ability of this method to create the stress-strain measures global response as well as local distribution has been demonstrated for both transverse uniaxial tensile stress state as well as equally-biaxial compressive deformation gradient state
3. For the first example, a good comparison with FEA results as well as with the orthogonal HFGMC has been shown. For the second example, the symmetry of the macroscale description of the problem using an equally-biaxial deformation-gradient was highly pronounced in the local stress field results

Future Work

1. Improve convergence using incremental-iterative algorithm solution
2. Multiscale analysis of structure that undergoes finite-strain
3. Extension for 3D RUCs

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